

EARLY MOBILITY AFTER SURGERY: A REVIEW OF ERAS GUIDELINES

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Keywords

Early ambulation

Enhanced Recovery After Surgery

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ABSTRACT

Early mobilization is a vital strategy that accelerates recovery following surgery, reduces the risk of complications, and enhances the quality of life. Prolonged postoperative bed rest has been linked to adverse outcomes such as muscle atrophy, insulin resistance, pulmonary dysfunction, and thromboembolic events. In contrast, initiating physical activity as early as possible—tailored to each patient's condition—supports physiological functions, including pain control, respiratory efficiency, lymphatic drainage, and muscle preservation. Early mobilization typically begins with bed-based exercises and gradually progresses to standing, walking, and engaging in daily self-care activities. This individualized approach is a core component of Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) protocols, which emphasize structured and goal-oriented mobilization strategies. Evidence from the literature and clinical studies has demonstrated that early mobilization leads to shorter ICU and hospital stays, quicker return to functional independence, reduced risk of complications like delirium and pressure ulcers, and improved patient outcomes across various surgical disciplines. In addition, ERAS guidelines from different specialties—including breast reconstruction, esophagectomy, liver transplantation, gastrectomy, and radical cystectomy—provide specific recommendations on the timing and implementation of early mobilization. These guidelines highlight the importance of structured mobilization plans, preoperative education, and multidisciplinary coordination to ensure patient safety and adherence. As a result, early mobilization is critical in the postoperative phase. In this context, guideline-based early mobilization strategies and step-by-step recommendations have been compiled to support healthcare professionals in the planning and implementation of safe and effective mobilization programs.

INTRODUCTION

Prolonged bed rest after surgery leads to increased urinary retention and insulin resistance in patients, while also contributing to physical dysfunctions such as muscle atrophy and a decrease in bone mass¹. Postoperative immobilization results in weakened pulmonary function and increases the risk of circulatory issues such as thromboembolism^{1,2}. In preventing these issues, the concept of postoperative early mobilization becomes crucial¹. Early mobilization refers to interventions aimed at restoring the lost mobility of conscious patients as soon as possible after surgery, through an individualized plan³. This process includes a series of movements, starting with bed exercises and progressing to standing, walking, and daily activities (such as transfers, using the toilet, dressing, and bathing)³.

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Early mobilization positively contributes to mucociliary clearance, enhancing alveolar ventilation efficiency and improving oxygen intake. It also provides physiological benefits such as reducing myocardial oxygen consumption and decreasing the workload on the heart⁴. Encouraging early mobilization in the postoperative period helps control postoperative pain and accelerates lymphatic drainage, thus reducing the formation of edema^{4,5}. Studies have shown that early mobilization shortens intensive care unit (ICU) and hospital stay durations, enables patients to reach functional independence more quickly, and reduces the duration of delirium^{6,7}. In a prospective cohort study by Morris et al.⁸, patients who underwent early mobilization had significantly shorter ICU (5.5 days vs. 6.9 days) and hospital stays (11.2 days vs. 14.5 days). In the research by Öztaş et al.⁹, early and planned mobilization programs post-surgery were found to reduce issues such as constipation and ileus, with positive effects on the time to first gas passage, first defecation, abdominal bloating severity, nausea/vomiting symptoms, and the initiation of oral intake⁹. Li et al.¹⁰ examined the effects of early mobilization after pancreatic surgery in a randomized controlled trial involving 135 patients. They found that early mobilized patients walked longer distances in the first week, leading

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to reduced muscle mass loss and insulin resistance, faster recovery, and earlier defecation¹⁰.

The results of studies in the literature indicate that early mobilization reduces morbidity and mortality, facilitates faster recovery of functional walking capacity, and enhances quality of life^{11,12}. Early and organized mobilization is recommended by the Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) guidelines due to its positive effects on patients¹³. In a study by Siddique et al.¹⁴, 30 patients who underwent traumatic brain surgery were assessed, and two different scales for bed sores were used to evaluate them 6 weeks before and after the intervention. Early mobilization and bed positioning therapies were observed to prevent or reduce the formation of pressure ulcers in these patients. Additionally, early mobilization helps regulate the ventilation/perfusion balance, increasing tidal volume and functional residual capacity, thereby preventing respiratory infections such as pulmonary embolism, pneumonia, and atelectasis in the postoperative period. It was also suggested that early mobilization could be beneficial in reducing or controlling pain levels¹³.

In a study by Laily et al.¹⁵, 28 patients undergoing transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP) were included. In this study, 71.4% of patients who did not undergo early mobilization developed bladder clotting, while 85.7% of those who were mobilized early did not experience clotting. Numerous studies conducted over the past 15 years have shown that early mobilization is both a safe and effective method^{5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,15,16,17,18,19}.

In addition to the literature, ERAS guidelines highlight the effectiveness of early mobilization in reducing hospital stays and increasing patients' levels of independence. The early mobilization recommendations from these guidelines are outlined below^{20,21,22,23,24}.

In the 2017 *Breast Reconstruction Guidelines* of ERAS, it is recommended that patients be encouraged to mobilize as soon as possible, ideally within the first 24 hours post-surgery²¹. In the 2018 *Esophagectomy Guidelines*, although there is a lack of strong evidence regarding the exact timing of mobilization, a standardized and structured approach is suggested. This includes the implementation of a preoperative prehabilitation program, starting mobilization on the day of surgery, defining mobilization goals, and using visual and written materials to explain the importance of each goal²². The 2022 *Liver Transplantation Guidelines* suggest that mobilization should be encouraged from the morning after the transplant until the day of discharge²⁰.

In the 2014 *Gastrectomy Guidelines*, it is stated that patients should be actively mobilized on the morning of postoperative day 1 and encouraged to meet daily mobility goals²³. In the 2013 *Radical Cystectomy Guidelines*, it is recommended that patients should be outside of their beds for 2 hours on postoperative day 0 and 6 hours on postoperative day 1²⁴. Additionally, the levels of evidence and recommendations for these guidelines are presented in Table I.

Table I : Eras guidelines recommendations for early mobilization ^{20,21,22,23,24}

Surgery Type	Postoperative Mobilization Recommendations	Evidence and Recommendation Level
Liver Transplantation (2022)	Mobilization should be encouraged from the morning after transplant until discharge.	Strong evidence, strong recommendation
Breast Reconstruction (2017)	Mobilization should be encouraged within the first 24 hours post-surgery.	Moderate evidence, strong recommendation
Esophagectomy (2018)	Standardized and structured approach recommended: preoperative prehabilitation program, mobilization on the day of surgery, and use of visual and written materials to explain goals.	Low to moderate evidence, conditional recommendation
Gastrectomy (2014)	Patients should be actively mobilized on the morning of postoperative day 1 and encouraged to meet daily mobility goals.	Strong evidence, strong recommendation
Radical Cystectomy (2013)	Patients should be outside the bed for 2 hours on postoperative day 0 and 6 hours on postoperative day 1.	Moderate evidence, strong recommendation

Achieving success postoperative outcomes requires not only the involvement of healthcare professionals but also the active participation of patients and their families. However, patients are often hesitant to engage in early mobilization due to concerns such as damaging the surgical site, experiencing nausea or dizziness, or feeling unprepared²⁵. Additional barriers include the presence of medical devices like urinary catheters or drains, fear of dislodging these devices, pain, and the risk of falling²⁶. These factors can significantly reduce patients' willingness to mobilize. To overcome these challenges and promote effective early mobilization, there is a need for specialized mobilization protocols developed in parallel with preoperative and postoperative Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) protocols²⁷. The components of these specialized mobilization protocols are detailed below.

1. Preoperative period interventions in early mobilization

In the preoperative period, while the patient's general health status and surgical risks are assessed, early mobilization strategies are also planned to optimize the recovery process. This approach helps reduce postoperative complications and supports the patient's faster recovery^{13,28}. Prerehabilitation and patient education play a critical role in ensuring that patients are informed about the necessity and importance of mobilizing as soon as possible post-surgery, which contributes to quicker mobilization. By addressing these factors, patients can be better prepared for the postoperative recovery process.

1.1 Prerehabilitation

Preoperative rehabilitation is a process that improves both the psychological and physical health of patients, preparing them more effectively for surgery²⁹. These programs focus on alleviating patients' physical symptoms, thereby enhancing their physical and emotional preparedness during the preoperative period³⁰. Additionally, these programs offer psychological benefits, helping patients cope with the body's stress responses and postoperative limitations³⁰. Preoperative education increases patients' awareness of the recovery process and facilitates more effective collaboration with the healthcare team³¹.

Preoperative personalized exercise programs can vary in type, including strength and aerobic exercises, among others¹⁴. Strength training, particularly depending on the body area to be surgically treated, may focus on resistance exercises aimed at strengthening core, hip, back, and upper body muscles³².

Aerobic exercises, on the other hand, may include activities such as walking or standing, tailored to the patient's physiological condition in terms of frequency and intensity³⁴. Proper and efficient implementation of these activities requires that patients be well-informed during the preoperative period.

1.2 Patient information

Preoperative mobilization of the patient requires educating and informing the patient about surgical expectations in order to maximize their functional and physical condition. Evidence linking delayed mobilization to increased pulmonary complications, reduced muscle strength, higher insulin resistance, and an elevated risk of thromboembolic complications should be communicated^{1,28}. Therefore, except for surgeries where postoperative bed rest is necessary, patients should be informed that, on the day of surgery, they should spend at least two hours out of bed, and in the following days, up to six hours daily out of bed until discharge^{2,34}. Additionally, some studies have shown that limited mobilization practices, such as sitting at the edge of the bed or standing, in patients in intensive care can lead to positive outcomes. Additionally, preoperative education provided under the ERAS protocol has been found to be effective in improving the general well-being of patients³⁵. Therefore, it is important to encourage the active participation of patients in mobilization¹.

2. Postoperative period applications in early mobilization

The postoperative period is the process that begins after the surgical procedure and continues until the patient has fully recovered¹³. Although this period varies depending on the type of surgery, the implementation of early mobilization strategies plays a critical role in accelerating the recovery process. Early mobilization reduces the risk of infections and complications, supports pain management, and accelerates the patient's functional rehabilitation²⁰. Therefore, encouraging early mobilization during the postoperative period ensures that the patient recovers more quickly and smoothly.

2.1. Patient assessment before early mobilization

Patients who start preoperative exercise programs are more likely to remain active after surgery compared to those undergoing "prerehabilitation" controls³⁶. In addition to this, fluid management, pain control, anemia management, and the items shown in Figure II should be implemented to assess the patient's compliance with mobilization.

In the postoperative period, for both groups, the following metrics can be recorded: the time of mobilization initiation, Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale (RASS) score, vital signs, the duration of time spent out of bed during each mobilization session, the number of steps taken, whether the target was achieved, the reason for failure to meet the target, and the total number of steps taken within 24 hours after surgery, using scales²⁷. Additionally, based on the patient's history and vital signs, the appropriate mobilization time should be determined according to the table showing all evaluations (Figure I)²⁶

2.2. Tests and scales that can be used in patient assessment for mobilization

2.2.1. Richmond agitation sedation scale (rass)

The Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale (RASS) was developed in 1989 by Cook and Palma to assess patients' levels of agitation and sedation. This scale uses positive scores to identify patients experiencing agitation, while negative scores indicate patients who are sedated or in a coma³⁷. For patients to be considered suitable for mobilization, a target RASS score of 0 is typically aimed for²⁷.

2.2.2. Six-minute walk test

This test was developed by Balka in the 1960s to measure the functional capacity of healthy individuals. The six-minute walk test is commonly used to assess the functional capacity of patients prior to surgery^{27,38}.

2.2.3. Visual analog scale (vas)

The Visual Analog Scale (VAS) is a valid, reliable, and practical measurement tool used to convert concepts that are difficult to quantify into numerical values. This scale is used to evaluate the time when patients start early mobilization and to progress smoothly to the next steps of mobilization. Additionally, the VAS scale has been used in various studies to evaluate the suitability of patients for early mobilization^{27,39,40}.

2.2.4. Hospital anxiety and depression scale (hads)

This scale is used to measure the levels and severity of anxiety and depression, as well as to identify the risk of anxiety and depression. It consists of a total of 14 items on a 4-point Likert scale, where odd-numbered questions assess anxiety and even-numbered questions assess depression. The cut-off points for the scale are 10/11 for the anxiety subscale and 7/8 for the depression subscale; scores above these thresholds are considered at risk⁴¹. Many studies have utilized the HADS

scale for the pre-assessment of early mobilization and have facilitated the acceleration of the mobilization process²⁶.

2.2.5. Pedometer applications

A pedometer is an electromechanical device that estimates the number of steps taken by the user and detects movement patterns. With the advancement of mobile technologies, pedometers have been integrated into various

platforms such as smartphones, smartwatches, and other wearable devices. When the application is activated, it can track the number of steps and walking distance even if the phone is carried in a bag or pocket³⁹. A study by Kızılcık Özkan et al.⁴² revealed that 84.6% of patients were satisfied with the use of pedometers and that early mobilization improved respiratory system function, as well as helping to shorten the hospital stay.

2.3. Progressive mobilization plan

Before initiating an early mobilization program, several key factors must be ensured. The first step is identifying the key personnel involved in the program, which is crucial. This includes creating a team with representatives from various disciplines such as nursing, physical therapy, respiratory therapy, and physicians⁴³. This team, working alongside nursing staff, will contribute to the mobilization efforts⁴⁴. Additionally, these individuals must be trained on mobility goals and mobilization protocols for all healthcare personnel⁴³.

Furthermore, establishing a good sedation protocol is of critical importance. This should include practices like the discontinuation of sedative medications, as patients may have difficulty participating in early mobilization activities if they are not at appropriate sedation levels, which can hinder mobilization^{Fig. I}.

Most studies examining the effectiveness of early mobilization have implemented specific early mobilization protocols. While there are numerous protocols, there is no single standard protocol. Early mobilization protocols typically include the following components: the patient population, inclusion and exclusion criteria for appropriate patients, safety guidelines related to mobilization, identification of individuals who should assist during mobilization, setting goals for mobilization, and tracking whether those goals have been achieved. Ideally, protocols should also include a monitoring

or feedback mechanism. Evidence suggests that mobilization along with a culture of quality improvement, contribute to protocols developed through a multidisciplinary approach better patient outcomes⁴⁵, Fig. 1. under strong leadership, aimed at addressing knowledge gaps,

Figure 1: Progressive patient mobilization steps⁴⁵

Figure 2: Mobilization procedure²⁶

There are various parameters that can be tolerated for early mobilization Fig. II. Common barriers encountered in intensive care units include severe illness, hemodynamic or respiratory instability, pain, agitation, and delirium. Process-related barriers involve issues such as a lack of coordination, incomplete or delayed screening and documentation, and unclear roles and responsibilities. Barriers related to ICU culture include insufficient sedation reduction, inadequate knowledge among staff regarding early mobilization, and the lack of prioritization of early mobilization. Structural barriers stem from factors like insufficient staffing, a lack of effective leadership, the absence of a structured program, and inadequate training. Additionally, the limited data on the cost-effectiveness of early mobilization creates challenges in persuading hospital administrators to support such a program^{11,16,46}. Multidisciplinary collaboration and effective leadership can assist in identifying barriers and implementing strategies to address them. The procedures outlined in Figures I and II can be applied to intensive care unit (ICU) patients who are intubated and receiving mechanical ventilation, those

undergoing non-invasive ventilation, or patients who do not require any airway support. Prior to any mobilization, a comprehensive assessment should be conducted to minimize risks, and safety criteria should be reviewed. Although such mobilization practices are used widely in ICUs, they typically have a low incidence of adverse outcomes (<2%). Despite the low risk, these practices are increasingly implemented as part of routine care in ICU settings^{26,45}.

The first two steps involve assessing the patient's level of consciousness and their ability to follow instructions (using the Richmond Agitation-Sedation Scale) and identifying any safety concerns that could hinder mobilization^{Fig. I and II, 47}. This evaluation is performed daily, with the goal of achieving the highest possible level of mobilization for the patient each day⁴⁸.

The team must also consider whether the patient has sufficient respiratory and cardiovascular reserve to perform the recommended mobilization. Additionally, it is important to assess whether the limits of organ support (such as adjusting ventilator settings or increasing vasoactive infusions) can be modified to support mobilization^{26,50}. If sedation can be reduced or factors hindering mobilization (e.g., timing of tests or procedures) can be overcome, mobilization is prioritized by healthcare professionals in the early hours of the day^{Fig. I}. If team members have doubts about continuing mobilization, this should be discussed with the intensive care physiotherapist and senior medical staff. The flowchart in Figure II emphasizes that the patient should be continuously monitored during mobilization^{26,48}.

During mobilization, imbalances in the patient's vital signs (e.g., a decrease in SpO₂ or an increase in heart rate) may occur, and in such cases, mobilization should be temporarily halted^{Fig. II}. If this happens, mobilization should be immediately stopped, and the patient should be placed in a resting position²⁶. In the very rare event of an adverse occurrence, mobilization should be stopped immediately, and the patient should be referred for urgent medical intervention^{48, 49}.

CONCLUSION

As a result, early mobilization is an important approach that accelerates the postoperative recovery process, reduces the risk

of complications, and improves patients' quality of life. Planned mobilization programs, particularly those implemented within the framework of ERAS protocols, shorten patients' hospital stay and positively impact the recovery process. Early mobilization has been proven to have several physiological benefits, such as reducing postoperative pain, insulin resistance, muscle loss, and respiratory complications.

Therefore, determining mobility goals through a multidisciplinary approach, training healthcare personnel, and implementing a patient-centered mobilization protocol play a significant role in postoperative patient care. In the future, further research in this field will contribute to enhancing the effectiveness of early mobilization practices and improving patient outcomes.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All of the authors declare that they have all participated in the design, literature review, writing and analysis of the paper, and that they have approved the final version.

REFERENCES

- Gustafsson UO, Scott MJ, Hubner M, Nygren J, Demartines N, Francis N, et al. Guidelines for perioperative care in elective colorectal surgery: Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS®) Society recommendations: 2018. *World Journal of Surgery*. 2019;43(3):659-695.
- Behairy AS, Mahmoud MAM, Deep SH. Evidence-based practice of early post-operative mobilization for Whipple surgery patients' selected outcomes. *Tanta Scientific Nursing Journal*. 2024;33(2).
- Hodgson CL, Bailey M, Young PJ. Early active mobilization during mechanical ventilation in the ICU. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2022;387(19):1747-1758
- Beliveau MM, Multach M. Perioperative care for the elderly patient. *Medical Clinics*. 2003;87(1):273-289.
- Drover JW, Dhaliwal R, Weitzel L, Wischmeyer PE, Ochoa JB, Heyland DK. Perioperative use of arginine-supplemented diets: A systematic review of the evidence. *Journal of the American College of Surgeons*. 2011;212(3):385-399.
- Shirvani F, Naji SA, Davari E, Sedighi M. Early mobilization reduces delirium after coronary artery bypass graft surgery. *Asian Cardiovascular and Thoracic Annals*. 2020;28(9):566-571.

7. Wang J, Ren D, Liu Y, Wang Y, Zhang B, Xiao Q. Effects of early mobilization on the prognosis of critically ill patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. 2020;110:103708.
8. Morris PE, Berry MJ, Files DC, Thompson JC, Hauser J, Flores L et al. Standardized rehabilitation and hospital length of stay among patients with acute respiratory failure: A randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*. 2016;315(24):2694-2702.
9. Öztas İ, Yava A, Koyuncu A. The effect of early mobilization on constipation after abdominal surgery: A systematic review. *Journal of Surgery and Medicine*. 2024;8(9):151-155.
10. Li Z, Zhou L, Li M, Wang W, Wang L, Dong W, Gong S. Early mobilization after pancreatic surgery: A randomized controlled trial. *Surgery*. 2024;176(4):1179-1188.
11. Needham DM, Korupolu R, Zanni JM, Pradhan P, Colantuoni E, Palmer JB et al. Early physical medicine and rehabilitation for patients with acute respiratory failure: A quality improvement project. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*. 2010;91(4):536-542.
12. Zhang L, Hu W, Cai Z, Liu J, Wu J, Deng Y, et al. Early mobilization of critically ill patients in the intensive care unit: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLOS ONE*. 2019;14(10):e0223185.
13. Aktaş D, Yılmaz K. The role of nurses in ERAS. In: Gündoğdu HR, Alkış N, Editors. *ERAS Book: Evidence-Based Surgery*. 1st ed. Ankara: Bayt Bilimsel Araştırmalar Basın Yayın ve Tanıtım Ltd. Şt.; 2023. p. 169-174.
14. Franssen RF, Janssen-Heijnen ML, Barberan-Garcia A, Vogelaar FJ, Van Meeteren NL, Bongers BC. Moderate-intensity exercise training or high-intensity interval training to improve aerobic fitness during exercise prehabilitation in patients planned for elective abdominal cancer surgery? *European Journal of Surgical Oncology*. 2022;48(1):3-13.
15. Laily NFR, Basri AH, Twistandayani R. Early mobilization on the incidence of stoele in post-op transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP) patients. *Journal of Nursing Application*. 2024;1(1):41-46.
16. Morris PE, Goad A, Thompson C, Taylor K, Harry B, Passmore L et al. Early intensive care unit mobility therapy in the treatment of acute respiratory failure. *Critical Care Medicine*. 2008;36(8):2238-2243.
17. Nydahl P, Sricharoenchai T, Chandra S, Kundt FS, Huang M, Fischill M et al. Safety of patient mobilization and rehabilitation in the intensive care unit: Systematic review with meta-analysis. *Annals of the American Thoracic Society*. 2017;14(5):766-777.
18. Hodgson CL, Stiller K, Needham DM, Tipping CJ, Harrold M, Baldwin CE et al. Expert consensus and recommendations on safety criteria for active mobilization of mechanically ventilated critically ill adults. *Critical Care*. 2014;18(6):658.
19. Siddique M, Mehrvi N, Niazi R, Nasir M. Effect of early mobilization and bed positioning on mobility among patients with traumatic brain injury. *Journal of Islamabad Medical & Dental College*. 2024;13(2):239-244.
20. Brustia R, Monsel A, Skurzak S, Schiffer E, Carrier FM, Patrono D, et al. Guidelines for perioperative care for liver transplantation: Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) recommendations. *Transplantation*. 2022;106(3):552-561.
21. Temple-Oberle C, Shea-Budgell MA, Tan M, Semple JL, Schrag C, Barreto M, et al. Consensus review of optimal perioperative care in breast reconstruction: Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) society recommendations. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*. 2017;139(5):1056e-1071e.
22. Low DE, Allum W, De Manzoni G, Ferri L, Immanuel A, Kuppasamy M, et al. Guidelines for perioperative care in esophagectomy: Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS®) society recommendations. *World Journal of Surgery*. 2019;43:299-330.
23. Mortensen K, Nilsson M, Slim K, Schäfer M, Mariette C, Braga M, et al. Consensus guidelines for enhanced recovery after gastrectomy. *Journal of British Surgery*. 2014;101(10):1209-1229.
24. Cerantola Y, Valerio M, Persson B, Jichlinski P, Ljungqvist O, Hubner M, et al. Guidelines for perioperative care after radical cystectomy for bladder cancer: Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS®) society recommendations. *Clinical Nutrition*. 2013;32(6):879-887.
25. Keener F. *Early mobilization of postoperative patients* [Doctoral dissertation, Jacksonville University]. 2024. [Accessed from: https://scholarworks.ju.edu/doctoral_dissertations and 12.12.2024].
26. Vermişli S, Çakmak Ö, Müezzinoğlu T, Aslan G, Baydur H. The effect of postoperative early mobilization on healing process and quality of life following radical cystectomy and ileal conduit: A randomized prospective controlled trial. *Journal of Urological Surgery*. 2022;9(1):9-19.
27. Koyuncu F, Iyigun E. The effect of mobilization protocol on mobilization start time and patient care outcomes in patients undergoing abdominal surgery. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. 2022;31(9-10):1298-1308.
28. Aksoy A, Yılmaz VD. A new approach to evidence-based practices in gynecological surgery: ERAS protocol and nursing. *Türkiye Klinikleri Journal of Nursing Science*. 2018;10(1):49-58.
29. West MA, Jack S, Grocott MP. Prehabilitation before surgery: Is it for all patients? *Best Practice & Research Clinical Anaesthesiology*. 2021;35(4):507-516.
30. Gillis C, Ljungqvist O, Carli F. Prehabilitation, enhanced recovery after surgery, or both? A narrative review. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*. 2022.
31. Zaki HA, Shaban EE, Shaban A, Alkahlout BH, Shallik NA, Azad AM. Perioperative preparation of emergency patients from emergency department to operating room. In: *New Insights in Perioperative Care*. IntechOpen; 2024. p. 1-22.
32. Hogg AJ. Feasibility of a short-term resistance and aerobic exercise prehabilitation program to enhance recovery in ENT cancer patients post-surgery. *Journal of Clinical Exercise Physiology*. 2021;8(2):49-59.
33. Siu ATY, Singh F, Ismail H, Newton RU. Preoperative aerobic exercise therapy prior to abdominal surgery: What is the evidence? What dose? *Current Anesthesiology Reports*. 2022.
34. ERAS Turkey Association. *Enhanced Recovery After Surgery in Turkey*. 2024. [Accessed from: <http://eras.org.tr/page.php?id=10&saglikcalisani=true> and 12.12.2024].
35. Işık G, Ünsal Atan Ş. Jinekolojik/onkolojide cerrahi sonrası iyileşmenin hızlandırılması protokolü. In: Özbayır T, Editor. *Cerrahi Sonrası İyileşmenin Hızlandırılması Protokolü ve Hemşirelik*. 1st ed. Ankara: Türkiye Klinikleri; 2021. p. 63-71.
36. Gillis C, Li C, Lee L, Rashami A, Berson A, Liberman AS, et al. Prehabilitation vs. rehabilitation: A randomized controlled trial in patients undergoing colorectal resection for cancer. *Anesthesiology*. 2014;121(5):937-947.
37. Ely EW, Truman B, Shintani A, Thomason JWW, Wheeler AP, Gordon S, et al. Monitoring sedation status over time in ICU patients: Reliability and validity of the Richmond Agitation-Sedation Scale (RASS). *JAMA*. 2003;289(22):2983-2991.
38. Holland AE, Spruit MA, Troosters T, Puhan MA, Pepin V, Saey D, et al. An official European Respiratory Society/American Thoracic Society technical standard: Field walking tests in chronic respiratory disease.

- European Respiratory Journal*. 2014;44(6):1428-1446.
39. Jin Z, Lee C, Zhang K, Jeong R, Gan TJ, Richman DC. Utilization of wearable pedometer devices in the perioperative period: A qualitative systematic review. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*. 2023;136(4):646-654.
 40. Clementsen SØ, Hammer OL, Benth JŠ, Jakobsen RB, Randsborg PH. Early mobilization and physiotherapy vs. late mobilization and home exercises after ORIF of distal radial fractures: A randomized controlled trial. *JBJS Open Access*. 2019;4(3):e0012.
 41. Aydemir O, Guvenir T, Küey L, Kültür S. Validity and reliability of the Turkish version of the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale. *Türk Psikiyatri Dergisi*. 1997;84:280-287.
 42. Kızılıcık Özkan Z, Gökçe Işık A, Ünver S, Yanık F. The effect of postoperative mobilization with a pedometer on pulmonary functions and length of postoperative hospital stay in patients undergoing lung resection: Cross-sectional study. *Türkiye Klinikleri Archives of Lung*. 2022;21(1):35-42.
 43. Schweickert W, Pawlik AJ, Kress JP. Physical therapy. In: Hall JB, Schmidt GA, Kress JP, Editors. *Principles of Critical Care*. 4th ed. McGraw-Hill Education; 2015.
 44. Bakhru RN, Wiebe DJ, McWilliams DJ, Spuhler VJ, Schweickert WD. An environmental scan for early mobilization practices in U.S. ICUs. *Critical Care Medicine*. 2015;43(11):2360-2369.
 45. Rawal H, Bakhru RN. How I Do It: Early Mobilization in the Intensive Care Unit. *CHEST Critical Care*. 2023;100038.
 46. Lord RK, Mayhew CR, Korupolu R, Manthey EC, Friedman MA, Palmer JB et al. ICU early physical rehabilitation programs: Financial modeling of cost savings. *Critical Care Medicine*. 2013;41(3):717-724
 47. Sessler CN, Gosnell MS, Grap MJ, Brophy GM, O'Neal PV, Keane KA et al. The Richmond Agitation-Sedation Scale: Validity and reliability in adult intensive care unit patients. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*. 2002;166(10):1338-1344.
 48. Green M, Marzano V, Leditschke IA, Mitchell I, Bissett B. Mobilization of intensive care patients: A multidisciplinary practical guide for clinicians. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*. 2016;9:247-256.
 49. Leditschke IA, Green M, Irvine J, Bissett B, Mitchell IA. What are the barriers to mobilizing intensive care patients? *Cardiopulmonary Physical Therapy Journal*. 2012;23(1):26-29.